

THE MEANING OF EMBROIDERY PATTERNS

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Abstract: In this article, the role of embroidery in life, its types, master-disciple traditions, types of decorative art, the meaning of colors are studied.

Аннотация: В данной статье изучается роль вышивки в жизни, ее виды, традиции мастера-ученика, виды декоративно-прикладного искусства, значение цветов.

It is no secret that the thousand-year history of the Uzbek people continues to amaze many countries today. The emergence of the first statehood of ancient tribes and the history of some dynasties are directly related to our people and our country. Among our people, there is a common saying in the family, parents who want their child to learn a trade must leave it completely at the disposal of the teacher so that he can become a master of this profession. has been following the tradition.

That is why, in ancient times, parents respected the teacher who taught their children a trade. The culture of relationship between parents and teachers has its own characteristics. Qualities such as showing love and kindness to the teacher, correctly understanding the teacher's rebuke to the child, providing the necessary things for the child to learn a trade, and pleasing the teacher are considered important factors in child education.

There are many types of art and their names.

One of the most common types of art is decorative applied art. This art includes the decoration of everyday objects, dishes, clothes, furniture, carpets, toys and the like. Decorative and practical works of art serve the tasks of satisfying people's daily life needs, adding beauty to the surroundings, the exterior and interior of houses. In addition, practical art helps a person to be self-confident and willful, to be patient. - creates a foundation for tolerance.

In most cases, the child's interest in the profession is formed on the basis of imitating his parents, brothers, relatives, that is, his elders. The representative of each family had to diligently study the craft belonging to his dynasty and teach his students its full secrets. Forming and educating a perfect person in society is an important task of the modern family. Because a person's interest in any trade or profession first of all arises in the family. A certain political-ideological worldview, moral standards, behavior patterns, and physical qualities are inculcated in a person through family upbringing. As a result of this process, which takes place in the family, the person ultimately assimilates social norms and values and enters social life. Embroidery, which is a part of decorative art, is one of the oldest crafts.

Embroidery plays an important role in decorating clothes and items. By knowing how to embroider, you can update clothes, decorate and prepare many necessary items, such as napkins, panels, aprons, pillowcases, and gifts for loved ones.

Embroidery is an interesting and creative work that can bring a lot of joy to a person, can be a pastime in his free time, and can bring a person to the world of sophistication. When learning embroidery techniques, everything may not turn out well at once, because embroidery requires patience, attention, order. Therefore, the embroiderer should be persistent. As you acquire the necessary practical skills and qualifications, the work will gradually become easier.

There is a centuries-old history of the art of embroidery, according to archeological findings, since ancient times, the embodiment of household items - towels, tablecloths, festive and everyday clothes, shawls, embroidery methods, flowers, colors has been passed down from generation to generation. It has been improving. Gradually, good embroideries were selected, and unique embroidery samples were created, characterized by national characteristics, and hats and other items were decorated with embroideries.

The items embroidered by folk craftsmen are distinguished by beautiful flowers, matching of colors, full proportions, and professional accuracy of execution methods. Each embroidered item has a practical function.

In the second half of the 19th century, the invention of the embroidery machine laid the foundation for the creation of embroidery enterprises. The large production of embroideries on the machine damaged their artistry, and as a result, flower embroideries began to be forgotten. But only some types have been preserved. Uzbek embroidery was enriched and developed under the influence of embroidery of neighboring nations. If we look at Uzbek embroidery, we can find the methods and styles of Indian, Chinese, Russian, Afghan, Kazakh, Kyrgyz and Tajik embroiderers.

Uzbek embroiderers have a lot of vegetal, geometric and flower patterns, while Russian embroideries depict a lot of geometric vegetal shapes, flowers, birds and fruits. In Kazakh and Kyrgyz embroidery, elements reminiscent of animals, horns and hooves are depicted. According to ancient traditions, Uzbek girls had to prepare all kinds of embroidery items for future brides' dowries. The finer and more beautiful the embroidery, the higher the value. Girls were taught to embroider from the age of 7-9. They begin to embroider independently after three or four years. Grown-up embroidery girls tried to express their dreams of beauty according to their art and nature.

In the recent past, the most developed types of Uzbek practical decorative art, such as embroidery, needlework, stone and bone carving, carving, knife making, beadwork, jewelry, goldsmithing, carpet making, felting, basketry, etc. execution technologies, real national names, their specific terms, schools, methods specific to these arts, and the services of masters who gained fame in these fields are known all over the world.

The art of embroidery of Central Asia has been known to the world since ancient times. In the past, the beauty of our ancestors' fabrics has not lost its charm to this day. The exquisite embroideries continue to amaze us until now. Embroidery is an Arabic word that means image, flower, and it is an ornament created by repetition of birds, animals, flora, geometric and other various forms in a certain order. Artistic embroidery is the art of creating beauty in the combination of colors and unique compositions. In his work, the craftsman skillfully uses the natural gloss and harmony of colors, the beautiful shape, the texture of the material, and achieves bright expression.

The embroidery compositions of each oases and cities are unique. For example, Tashkent, Khorezm, Fergana, Samarkand, Bukhara, Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya embroidery

schools have their own shapes and colors. In the process of creating an independent composition, embroidery elements are interconnected by stylization. Attention is paid to the functions and smooth drawing of embroidery pieces. A composition is made from flower, leaf, branch, ax and bird embroidery elements.

It is known that any pattern is used to decorate things, i.e. dishes, clothes, gazmol, building, avenue and the like. When drawing a pattern, mainly two forms are used, i.e. natural and geometric forms. Plants, animals and birds are the object of the art of patterning. Leaf, tulip, pepper, rose, cotton, pomegranate, pear, egg, grape, peacock, pigeon, mouse, butterfly, fox, turtle, bird, lion, goose, fish, beetle, samovar, kettle telephone, the appearance of a star, kettle and other objects can be used as a basis for the pattern.

Each nation has its own traditions and characteristics. For example, Ukrainian folk patterns show more sunflowers, deer, birds, wheat and other things, while Kyrgyz and Kazakh patterns depict animals and their kings, grasses. Tajik folk motifs include tulips, almonds, and various flowers; Turkmen folk motifs often depict goat heads, vines, and birds, while typical Uzbek folk motifs include leaves, flowers, buds, tulip buds, peppers, pomegranates, pomegranate leaves, pears, and many others. is expressed.

Uzbek folk patterns have the following unique customs and features:

The content of Islamic forms. Almonds - happiness. Leaf - spring awakening.

Pepper - protection from all kinds of evil, spicy food. Rose flower (gulsafsar) - peace and longevity. Pomegranate - goodness, hairiness, hairiness. The moon is a symbol of happiness. Apple is a symbol of love. Branch - wealth and prosperity. Leaf - toklik spring awakening, nowruz. Isriq is a symbol of protection from the evil eye. Rose is a symbol of beauty

Content in the form of birds and animals.

The lion is a symbol of bravery, courage and strength. Fox - cunning. An ant is a symbol of wisdom and modesty. Nightingale - loyalty. Huma is a bird that brings happiness. Owl - unhappiness ruin. Fish is a symbol of vigilance. A mouse is a sign of the increase of domestic animals. A goat's or ram's horn is a symbol of courage, bravery and purity.

White dove - peace. Reading - beauty, vulnerability, tenderness.

Color content

Green is a symbol of mother nature. Blue color is a symbol of blue sky, peace and protection from bad weather. Red color - victory, joy and happiness. Yellow color - sanctity. Black color - mourning. Yellow flower - separation. Zangori is a high faith. White color is a symbol of purity, light, happiness and luck.

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